

USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN STUDYING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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***Abstract.** In the article is given the problem of using artificial intelligence (AI) technologies for teaching a foreign language at university. A review of scientific and methodological literature on the use of AI in education is given. AI services designed for teaching foreign languages, as well as AI tools that act as teacher assistants are considered. The linguodidactic capabilities of chatbots are analyzed. Options for AI-based tasks for organizing the educational process are presented.*

***Key words:** artificial intelligence; teaching foreign languages; educational technology; virtual educational; chatbot, chat GPT, virtual educational platform, electronic educational resource.*

Currently, there is a boom in the development of neural networks and chatbots in many areas of life, images, texts, questions, mind maps and other educational materials in a few seconds upon user request. Chatbots are able to maintain a conversation, answer a question, comment on the work done, and also give recommendations on how it can be improved. In this regard, many teachers have quite justified concerns: since students can write essays and complete other tasks designed to practice language skills with the help of AI, there is no point in assigning homework.

An analysis of scientific and methodological literature devoted to the study of the use of artificial intelligence in education was conducted from the point of view of prospects and possible risks. Artificial intelligence services were analyzed for functionality and potential for implementation in the process of teaching a foreign language. To create tasks based on AI, empirical experience of working with AI services in practical foreign language classes for students of different areas of professional training was used.

Scientific and methodological literature states that many professions are being transformed as a result of such digitalization, including the profession of a foreign language teacher. The directions of such transformation are named as “the development of online educational platforms, the replacement of “live” specialists with virtual reality and artificial intelligence” [1, p. 22]. The teacher as a “talking head” or a transmitter of knowledge, not being the only possible means and channel of learning, is losing its demand and relevance. New roles and functions appear - tutor, moderator, developer of educational trajectories, organizer of project-based learning, coordinator of online educational platforms, game teacher [2, p. 43].

A foreign language teacher must be able to use digital tools, programs and online resources for teaching a foreign language, create their own digital teaching materials and digital environments, organize the learning process in a digital environment and manage it. A teacher who does not have a high level of digital competence will not be able to use AI technologies in the educational process to the fullest extent [3, p.120].

According to a policy brief from the UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education, AI will play a key role in implementing the idea of personalized learning, namely adapting the content of learning and the pace of the learning process to the specific needs of each student [4].

There are several fairly effective online resources for editing texts in a foreign language that use AI technologies. One such resource is Grammarly, which corrects more than 150 types of errors, such as errors in grammar, spelling, punctuation, writing style, and sentence structure. If there are errors, Grammarly provides recommendations for their correction, offering various options. Working with this service allows students to analyze their texts, developing critical thinking skills, which can be useful in the future when writing term papers, master's theses, research articles, abstracts, and other written works.

On the issue of replacing a foreign language teacher with artificial intelligence, the GPT chat itself commented on this problem as follows: “Artificial intelligence has the potential to complement and improve the educational process, but a direct replacement of teachers is unlikely. Unlike AI, teachers have the skills of empathy, motivation and social interaction. Teachers are better able to understand the context and explain the material taking into account different points of view and nuances, encouraging critical thinking and the formation of their own opinions.

Work in the direction of using AI for teaching foreign languages is very promising and should be continued not only in terms of developing new AI tools, but also in terms of creating algorithms and mechanisms for interaction between teachers and students with AI, as well as systems of corresponding tasks.

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